

Oxidation of hydrazine and hydroxylamine by vanadium(V) under the conditions where VO_2^+ and decavanadates coexist

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Manuscript received 28 October 1999, revised 16 October 2000, accepted 8 December 2000

The kinetics of oxidation of hydrazine and hydroxylamine have been investigated in the pH range 3.1–4.3. Both the oxidations obey first order kinetics with respect to the reductant, but the rate has very little dependence on $[\text{V}^V]_t$. The reactions are accelerated by H^+ ion but the dependence of rate on $[\text{H}^+]$ is less than that corresponding to first order dependence. Under these conditions, the species, VO_2^+ is in equilibrium with decavanadate ions and the equilibrium accounts for the different kinetic pattern observed in this pH range.

In strongly acidic solutions vanadium(V) exists only in the form of VO_2^+ , whereas in the region of pH 2.0–4.3, it exists as decavanadates $\text{H}_2\text{V}_{10}\text{O}_{28}^{4-}$, $\text{HV}_{10}\text{O}_{28}^{5-}$ and VO_2^+ ^{1–5}. It is interesting to study the kinetic patterns of V^V oxidations when all these species are present and in mutual equilibrium. A detailed study of this nature has not so far been reported excepting that by Pickering and McAuley⁶ who investigated the kinetics of oxidation of mercaptosuccinic acid by vanadium(V) in this pH range. They obtained consistent results and stated that the interconversion of decavanadates and VO_2^+ takes place within the time of mixing. However, these workers studied the kinetics under the conditions, $[\text{substrate}] \gg [\text{V}^V]$ from which much information could not be obtained regarding kinetic patterns in this pH range. To obtain detailed information about the kinetic patterns and also assess the reactivities of vanadium(V) species, it is necessary to carry out the kinetic study keeping $[\text{V}^V]_t$ much higher than $[\text{substrate}]$. Such a study has now been attempted taking hydrazine and hydroxylamine as the reductants. The study has shown that there is a radical change in kinetic pattern of V^V oxidations when decavanadates and VO_2^+ are present than under the strongly acid conditions where only VO_2^+ species exists.

Results and Discussion

Both these reactions have been investigated earlier⁷ in strong acid media where VO_2^+ is the only species that is present. Under these conditions each of these oxidations obeys first order kinetics with respect to the substrate and the order with respect to vanadium(V) lies between 1 and 2. But in the pH range 3.1–4.3, where the solution contains the decavanadates, which are in equilibrium with VO_2^+ , entirely different kinetic pattern has been noticed. Under these

conditions, each of these reactions obeys first order kinetics with respect to the substrates but the dependence of rate on $[\text{V}^V]_t$ is not appreciable where $[\text{V}^V]_t$ is the total vanadium concentration in monomeric form (Tables 1 and 2)

Table 1 Effect of $[\text{V}^V]$ and pH on rate

$10^2 [\text{V}^V]$ mol dm^{-3}	pH	$10^4 k'$ s^{-1}
1.0	3.42	2.70
3.0	3.42	2.78
5.0	3.42	2.80
8.0	3.42	2.85
2.0	3.10	2.84
2.0	3.42	2.74
2.0	3.79	2.66
2.0	3.94	2.60
2.0	4.24	2.45

The kinetic results can be analysed considering the possible equilibria^{1–4} present under these conditions. In this pH range, vanadium(V) is present in the form of VO_2^+ , $\text{HV}_{10}\text{O}_{28}^{5-}$ and $\text{H}_2\text{V}_{10}\text{O}_{28}^{4-}$, related by the equilibria,

From eqm. (2), the concentrations of the $\text{H}_2\text{V}_{10}\text{O}_{28}^{4-}$ and $\text{HV}_{10}\text{O}_{28}^{5-}$ are related to the total decavanadate concentration by eqn. (3),

Table 2. Influence of $[V^V]$ and pH on rate

$[NH_2OH] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,

Temp. = $25.0 \pm 0.10^\circ$

$10^2 [V^V]$ mol dm^{-3}	pH	$10^4 k'$ s^{-1}
1.0	3.42	1.70
2.0	3.42	1.88
3.0	3.42	1.70
4.0	3.42	1.73
5.0	3.42	1.92
6.0	3.42	2.01
7.0	3.42	2.11
2.0	3.10	2.31
2.0	3.66	1.59
2.0	3.79	1.38
2.0	3.94	1.26
2.0	4.24	0.97

$$[H_2V_{10}O_{28}^{4-}] = [\text{Decavanadate}]_t [H^+] / (K_2 + [H^+]) = [H^+] \{ [V^V]_t - [VO_2^+] / 10 \} / (K_2 + [H^+])$$

$$\text{and } [HV_{10}O_{28}^{5-}] = [\text{Decavanadate}]_t - [H_2V_{10}O_{28}^{4-}] = \{ K_2 [V^V]_t / 10 \} / (K_2 + [H^+]) \quad (3)$$

and $[VO_2^+]$ (eqn. 1) is given by

$$[VO_2^+] = \{ K_1 [H_2V_{10}O_{28}^{4-}] \}^{0.1} [H^+]^{1.4} \quad (4)$$

and

$$[VO_2^+] = \{ (K_1 ([V^V]_t - [VO_2^+]) / 10) [H^+] / (K_2 + [H^+]) \}^{0.1} [H^+]^{1.4} \quad (5)$$

Applying the Newton-Raphson iteration method to eqn. (5), we calculated the concentration of $[VO_2^+]$ in this pH range. Its concentration has been found to be in the order $10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ which is far less than $[V^V]_t$. Hence, $[VO_2^+]$ under these conditions is fairly accurately obtained from eqn. (6),

$$[VO_2^+] = \{ K_1 ([V^V]_t / 10) [H^+] / (K_2 + [H^+]) \}^{0.1} [H^+]^{1.4} \quad (6)$$

It has been reported⁷ that in strong acid media VO_2^+ forms a 1 : 1 complex with each of these substrates which undergoes intramolecular electron-transfer forming products, and in the present conditions also the same steps in the redox processes can be envisaged with VO_2^+ species in addition to the steps involving the oxidations by $H_2V_{10}O_{28}^{4-}$ and $HV_{10}O_{28}^{5-}$. We believe that unprotonated forms of the reductants, N_2H_4 and NH_2OH , are the active reducing species because from these species the electrons can be ab-

stracted more easily compared to the protonated forms $N_2H_5^+$ and NH_3OH^+ ,

where, $S = N_2H_4$ or NH_2OH = $5.95 \text{ (} NH_3OH^+ \text{)}^8$

The concentration of the unprotonated substrate, S, is given by

$$[S] = \frac{K_a [HS^+]_t}{[H^+]} \quad \because [H^+] \gg K_a \quad (7)$$

where, $[HS^+]_t$ is the total concentration of either reductant.

A general scheme of rate-determining stages of these two reactions can now be written to analyse the kinetic results,

The scheme gives the rate-law,

$$-\frac{d[HS^+]_t}{dt} = k_1 [VO_2S^+] + k_2 [H_2V_{10}O_{28}^{4-}] [S] + k_3 [HV_{10}O_{28}^{5-}] [S] \quad (8)$$

By applying the equilibrium method⁹, $[VO_2S^+]$ is given by the equation,

$$[VO_2S^+] = K_3 K_a [VO_2^+] [HS^+]_t / (K_a + [H^+] + K_3 K_a [VO_2^+]) \quad (9)$$

And from eqns. (3)–(9), the rate-law assumes the form,

$$-\frac{d[HS^+]_t}{dt} = \frac{k_1 K_3 K_a \left\{ \frac{K_1 \left(\frac{[V^V]_t}{10} \right) [H^+]}{K_2 + [H^+]} \right\}^{0.1} [H^+]^{0.4} [HS^+]_t}{1 + K_3 K_a \left\{ \frac{K_1 \left(\frac{[V^V]_t}{10} \right) [H^+]}{K_2 + [H^+]} \right\}^{0.1} [H^+]^{0.4}}$$

$$\frac{k_2 K_a \left(\frac{[V^V]_t}{10} \right) [H^+] [S]_t}{K_2 + [H^+]} + \frac{k_3 K_2 K_a \left(\frac{[V^V]_t}{10} \right) [S]}{K_2 + [H^+]} \quad (10)$$

Since, the rate has very little dependence on $[V^V]_t$, the second and third terms in eqn. (10) do not contribute significantly and can be neglected and the pseudo-first order rate constant, k' , is given by

$$k' = \frac{k_1 K_3 K_a \left\{ \frac{K_1 \left(\frac{[V^V]_t}{10} \right) [H^+]}{K_2 + [H^+]} \right\}^{0.1} [H^+]^{0.4}}{1 + K_3 K_a \left\{ \frac{K_1 \left(\frac{[V^V]_t}{10} \right) [H^+]}{K_2 + [H^+]} \right\}^{0.1} \cdot [H^+]^{0.4}} \quad (11)$$

The rate equation satisfactorily explains all the kinetic features. The order with respect to substrate is one according to the equation. $([V^V]_t/10)^{0.1}$ varies from 0.50 to 0.62 as $[V^V]_t$ is varied from 1.0×10^{-2} to 8.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³. The term $([V^V]_t/10)^{0.1}$ is present in both numerator and denominator, further reducing the dependence of the k' on $[V^V]_t$, which explains very small dependence of rate on $[V^V]_t$. As required by the rate law, a plot of $1/k'$ vs $1/\{([H^+]/(K_2 + [H^+]))^{0.1} [H^+]^{0.4}\}$ at constant $[V^V]_t$ is a straight-line with positive slope and intercept, and from the values of slopes and intercepts, k_1 and $K_a K_3$ have been calculated (Table 3).

Table 3

Temp = 25 ± 0.1°	k_1 ± 0.2 × 10 ⁻⁴ s ⁻¹	$K_a K_3$
[Substrate]		
Hydrazine	3.0	95.6 ± 5.0
Hydroxylamine	5.8	4.5 ± 0.5

The mechanism does not involve the step,

that was postulated for the reaction in the strong acid media⁷ and substantiated by the presence of square term, $[V^V]^2$

in the rate law. In the present experimental conditions, such a dependence has not been found. In these pH media also hydrazine and $[V^V]_t$ react in the mole ratio 1 : 4 just as was observed in strongly acid media, nitrogen being the product of oxidation of hydrazine. This is possible only if two electron-transfer between hydrazine and V^V occurs¹⁰ giving N_2H_2 and V^{III} . N_2H_2 is oxidized in a two-electron step with V^V giving N_2 and V^{III} . V^{III} is rapidly oxidized by V^V giving vanadyl ion which is the final product.

In the case of hydroxylamine, $[VO_2 NH_2 OH]^+$ decomposes⁷ into $V^{2+} + [NH_2 O]^*$ which gives N_2 and $H_2 O$,

This is consistent with the 1 : 1 stoichiometry observed in the reaction.

Experimental

All the solutions were prepared using triple-distilled water. Sodium vanadate, hydrazine and hydroxylamine solutions were prepared and standardized¹¹. pH of the reaction mixture was maintained constant using acetic acid-acetate buffer. Ionic strength was maintained constant using standard sodium perchlorate solution.

The course of the reaction cannot be followed by measuring the absorbance due to V^V because of the presence of decavanadates in equilibrium with VO_2^+ and Beer's law is not obeyed. The reaction was followed by measuring the increase in absorbance due to the product VO_2^+ at 750 nm using a Shimadzu UV-260 spectrophotometer where all the other materials concerned have negligible absorbance. This method was employed earlier with success¹². Since the molar absorbance of VO_2^{2+} at 750 nm is small, long-path cells (5 cm) were used. Kinetic runs were carried out in duplicate and the rate data agreed within 7%.

The stoichiometry of the reaction in the pH range 3.1–4.3, was determined by mixing a known concentration of the substrate with a known excess of vanadium(v). After completion of the reaction (indicated by the constancy of absorbance with time) unreacted vanadium(v) was determined by titration with standard iron(II) after acidifying the reaction mixture to bring the acid concentration to 1.0 N, adding syrupy phosphoric acid (5 ml) and using barium

diphenylamine sulfonate as indicator. In the case of hydrazine, 4 moles of vanadium(V) (stoichiometric V^v in monomeric form) were consumed by one mole of hydrazine. In the oxidation of hydroxylamine, 1 mole of monomeric vanadium(V) was consumed by 1 mole of the substrate. These results are identical to those obtained in strong acid medium⁷ where N₂ was found to be the product of oxidation.

Vanadium(V) and the substrate were mixed in the stoichiometric quantities and after completion of the reaction, the absorption spectrum of the reaction mixture coincided with that of aqueous vanadium(IV) of the same concentration with identical molar absorptivity ($18.0 \pm 2 \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (G.R.B.) thanks U.G.C., New Delhi for funding.

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